

From Pixels to Meshes: The Evolution of 2D-to-3D Construction Techniques

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Contents

Abstract	5
Introduction	6
1	7
1.1 Digital 3D models and Novel View Synthesis	7
1.2 Light-based (Plenoptic) Methods (1996)	8
1.3 View-dependent Texture Mapping and Unstructured Light-Based Capture (1996-2001)	13
2 3D Construction before deep learning	22
2.1 Structure from Motion (SfM)	22
2.2 SfM + Multi-View Stereo (SOTA pre-deep-learning)	29
3 Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) and Gaussian Splatting	38
3.1 NeRF: Representing Scenes as Neural Radiance Fields	38
3.2 3D Gaussian Splatting for Real-Time Radiance Field Rendering	40
4 Results and Comparison	43
Conclusion	48
Bibliography	49

Abstract

Reconstructing three-dimensional (3D) mappings from two-dimensional (2D) images is a century-old problem solved with physical and digital techniques. This thesis revisits classical methods, analyzes modern ones, and implements a simple model derived from the current cutting-edge. The thesis attempts to recreate history and understand pain points to be addressed in the future.

The narrative develops over plenoptic methods, the methods that made it feasible to achieve acceptable quality of novel views. Then it evolves into intermediary techniques: Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and Multi-View Stereo (MVS), which rely on geometric constraints and photometric consistency. The main focus, however, is on the mathematical understanding of the modern techniques, and their applications: neural implicit methods, with a focus on Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) and 3D Gaussian Splatting, which is the current state of the art paradigm.

Projective geometry, radiance modeling, and differentiable volume rendering are presented to unify old and new approaches mathematically. Quantitative and qualitative comparisons highlight trade-offs in fidelity, speed, and complexity will be mentioned in the final section.

This thesis aims to equip the reader with a strong foundational understanding of 3D reconstruction techniques.

Introduction

Research Motivation and Research Question

Digital 3D modeling is an unwieldy art that requires both artistic capability and computational optimization expertise, and was mainly reserved for research centers and large entities to perform. With the development of the GPU, Graphics APIs (OpenGL, DirectX, Vulkan) and subsequent rendering engines (Blender, Unreal, Unity) the computational knowledge requirement has been democratized. Knowledge of these tools allows any user to implement visually extremely refined graphics whilst focusing fully on the art.

Light-based novel view synthesis methods have carved a path for the current neural and Gaussian novel view synthesis methods. These modern methods are strongly converging towards democratizing the artistic skills part of the equation.

My goal is to create a historical pathway that relates and explains the earliest methods of image-based rendering in a 3D point cloud, to the highest level of Gaussian splatting and newer methods. Due to extremely rapid development, especially post-NeRF (2022) and the numerous applications of the current state of the art, the thesis will mainly explore modern techniques.

Thesis Structure

This thesis is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the historical (mainly light-based) techniques.
- **Chapter 2** Delves into the previous state-of-the-art (COLMAP structure from motion) that carried novel view synthesis into what it is today.
- **Chapter 3** dives into Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) and 3D Gaussian Splatting, detailing their representation techniques, rendering process, and variations.
- **Chapter 4** presents a comparison among techniques explored in terms of compute, historical importance, and direct output results.
- **Conclusion** Includes open challenges, computational limitations, author's remarks and the conclusion.

Chapter 1

1.1 Digital 3D models and Novel View Synthesis

What is novel view synthesis? It is a class of techniques and algorithms that output new camera angles to an input of given camera angle image(s). The 4D lumigraph function and the light field function form the inception of this field.

3D digital objects begin with modeling the geometric and surface attributes of the objects in the environment along with any lights. These objects are formed by connecting edges, vertices, and polygons. Polygonal meshes (Meshes are collections of polygons) are the most common version of 3D objects, and a texture is mapped onto the mesh to give the exterior coloring and complex form.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the 3D modeling process (primitive creation and vertex addition). Image source: 3D Studio Co., “What Is 3D Modeling? Definition, Software & Processes”. Accessed April 7, 2025. <https://3dstudio.co/what-is-3d-modeling/>

2D-to-3D construction is where both of these elements meet; Novel view synthesis renders the unseen camera views of the image, and these images are used as input to

output a fully fleshed 3D digital model.

As this is a very newly developing field, large portions of all breakthrough can be covered at a fast pace in this journal.

1.2 Light-based (Plenoptic) Methods (1996)

The Lumigraph (1996)

The Lumigraph is the second part of the classical digital novel view synthesis technique duo, it is a faster, independent alternative to traditional geometric representation methods, which depend on geometric attributes and illumination complexity of a scene.

Lumigraph was born out of the need that computer graphics lacked the necessary means to “recreate much of the complex geometry and subtle lightning effects found in the real world” [6]. Beyond creating novel views, even faithful replication of views through given accurate geometric and optical flow models had not been achieved. Both this technique and the light-based plenoptic function were born from the work of Quicktime VR[4]. As these are the first computational applications, the research will be analysed from this point onward. This method, the lumigraph, is a 4D representation and computational application of a plenoptic function. The plenoptic function is a five dimensional quantity describing the flow of light at every 3D spatial position (x, y, z) for every 2D direction (θ, ϕ) . [6]

The plenoptic function can be mapped from 5D to 4D through considering only the subset of light leaving a bounded object. As shown in Figure 1.2, this reduction can be parameterized by rays in a 4D space, where a point in the 4D Lumigraph is described by its spatial and angular coordinates. It derives this idea and many similar ideas from the physical holographic stereogram design [6].

Figure 1.2: Page from Gortler et al. (SIGGRAPH 96) discussing the reduction of the 5D plenoptic function to the 4D Lumigraph and its parameterization (Figures 1 and 2 from the original paper are shown). Image source: ACM Digital Library.

There are multiple ways to parametrize from 5D to 4D from the plenoptic function, but here the one most similar to the digital holographic stereogram was chosen. One starts by drawing a box around the object of interest and focus on one face, parameterize the two sides of that face as s and t axes. Then one draws a second parallel plane to the face with sides (s, t) and labels its axes as (u, v) , then any point in the Lumigraph can be shown as (s, t, u, v) . The origin is placed at the center of the uv plane and st plane is located at $z = 1$, where z axis is normal to the uv plane [6].

Figure 1.3: Figure 3 from Gortler et al. (SIGGRAPH 96), illustrating the relationship between the 4D Lumigraph parameterization (s, t, u, v) and a pixel in an arbitrary image plane relative to the camera center.

If one intends to recreate the pixel of a novel view, the image coloring output of the pixel is given by the value $L(s, t, u, v)$. Figure 2.3 depicts that one conversely reaches the function $L(s, t, u, v)$ by taking an arbitrary existing image, position and orientation of the camera, and then constructs the Lumigraph function. This parameterization can be done rapidly in texture mapping operations built into modern hardware [6].

Lumigraph function $L(s, t, u, v)$ can be represented discretely by choosing M subdivisions of st axes and N subdivisions of uv axes. A grid point in st is indexed as (s_i, t_j) , in uv they are indexed as (u_p, v_q) . The RGB triple of a given pixel x is referred to as $x_{i,j,p,q}$.

The basis function $B_{i,j,p,q}$ corresponds to each point on the grid. Then a finite-dimensional Lumigraph function (\tilde{L}) can be approximated via the following linear combination [6]:

$$\tilde{L}(s, t, u, v) = \sum_{i=0}^M \sum_{j=0}^M \sum_{p=0}^N \sum_{q=0}^N x_{i,j,p,q} B_{i,j,p,q}(s, t, u, v)$$

The function is constrained to the vector space generated by the chosen set of basis functions.

We have given a basis for a finite-dimensional \tilde{L} and took our ideal, continuous L as input by reconstructing it from existing camera views, however one must still define a projection from L to \tilde{L} . This is when the existing views (L) are used for the synthesis of the novel view (\tilde{L}). For L^2 distance metric, which performs the closest representation to the original image, one can integrate L against the duals of the basis functions, given by the inner products. [6] $x_{i,j,p,q} = \langle L, \tilde{B}_{i,j,p,q} \rangle$

This forms the mathematical basis of the technique. Given a requirement for a higher resolution, N must be as close as possible to the final image resolution. This is because the uv plane is inherently closer to the final image and N is the resolution of the plane. In the case of M a low resolution is sufficient as the optical information flowing out from points on the uv plane can be assumed to not change significantly.

Geometric information on the ray (s, u) enhances the model furthermore, however is not fundamental to the understanding of the technique. Geometric information provides a remapping of u and v to u' and v' , with the new basis changing into: $B'_{i,j,p,q}(s, t, u, v) = B_{i,j,p,q}(s, t, u', v')$. In practice, the data suffers from two problems which are not addressed by this logic:

1) The sample points in the domain come as video pixel input from a hand-held camera, thus by the unpredictable positions the data can't be pre-specified. The dataset is also large (10^8) in a 4-dimensional space. Computing large linear equations is impractical [6].

2) Some regions have very sparse samples with significant gaps in data coverage. Sampling density is also very typically non-uniform [6].

To address both issues, the algorithm works in a three-step approach. The first step is called *splat*.

During splatting, one computes coefficients using Monte-Carlo integration with the following weighted average estimator:

$$w_i^0 = \sum_k \tilde{B}_i(s_k), \quad x_i^0 = \frac{1}{w_i^0} \sum_k \tilde{B}_i(s_k) L(s_k).$$

where for sample k , $[s_k]$ denotes the domain location.

During the pull phase, "lower resolution approximations of the function are derived using a set of wider kernels" [6]. One computes these wider kernels through summing together the higher resolution kernels with a discrete sequence \mathbf{h} . Lower resolutions are computed through combination of higher resolution coefficients with \mathbf{h} . A possible choice to compute would be:

$$w_i^{r+1} = \sum_k \tilde{h}_{k-2i} w_k^r, \quad x_i^{r+1} = \frac{1}{w_i^{r+1}} \sum_k \tilde{h}_{k-2i} w_k^r x_k^r.$$

The last step push is when the low weight (low confidence) regions in higher resolution are filled using lower resolution approximations. For higher confidence regions, lower resolution information is completely disregarded. From the lower resolution, one first creates temporary values for high resolution, low weight regions by upsampling and "convolving with a sequence h " [6] that satisfies

$$B_i^{r+1} = \sum_k \tilde{h}_{k-2i} B_k^r$$

. The temporary values are created by:

$$tw_i^r = \frac{1}{w_i^r} \sum_k h_{i-2k} \min(w_k^{r+1}, 1), \quad tx_i^r = \frac{1}{w_i^r} \sum_k h_{i-2k} \min(w_k^{r+1}, 1) x_k^{r+1}.$$

then these values are blended with the x and w values already present at level r :

$$x_i^r = tx_i^r (1 - w_i^r) + w_i^r x_i^r, \quad w_i^r = tw_i^r (1 - w_i^r) + w_i^r.$$

This is how the lumigraph function method applies to compute novel-views in practice. There are attempts made for 2D-to-3D object construction, however all of them have strong hardware and memory storage requirements. "Despite over 20 years of research, the reliable extraction of accurate 3D geometric information from imagery [...] remains elusive." [6].

Light Field Rendering (1996)

This is a technique based on the 5D plenoptic function and uses the same condition of free-space light representation to reduce the plenoptic function to 4D. This happens because radiance does not change unless the ray is blocked. Again, like the lumen function, represents that 4D space in two-dimensional slices [9].

As one can see from Figure 1.4, this technique employs a parametrization that uses two planes in arbitrary positions, one closer to the object (or the view) than the other [9]:

Figure 1: The light slab representation.

Figure 1.4: Figure 1 from Levoy and Hanrahan (1996), illustrating the light-slab representation of the 4D light field: rays parameterized by two parallel planes at (u, v) and (s, t) relative to the camera center [9].

Which is again the same concept from the lumigraph. One difference here is that the *light slabs* is the main focus of this technique for novel view synthesis.

If a singular slab were to contain all the rays hitting on the convex hull of the object, then that would be the ideal slab capable of reproducing any view. However with one slab this is not possible and one uses multiple slabs in specific arrangements to approach this ideal. Slabs forming parallel planes "generate fairly uniform patterns" [9].

Light slabs for virtual environments are images. The vantage point for the camera must be from the sample points (u, v) , and the image plane of the camera must lie on the (s, t) . Repeating this for every (u, v) will result in an array of possible images.

the (s, t) sampling location must be consistent for each camera shot, which is achieved with *sheared perspective projection* and each pixel corresponds to one sample.

Real images impose multiple problems; the lightning must be a static light field, and the whole scene must be well illuminated, while not possessing any unwanted shadows [9].

Another difference with this technique compared to the lumigraph is the focus on physical simplifying conditions for real images: They decided on working with images that are flyaround views of small objects instead of flythroughs of large scenes, they used a computer-controlled camera to predetermine the camera pose instead of computing it with human-made images. They used a spherical camera motion instead of a planar

Figure 1.5: Figure 12 from Levoy and Hanrahan (1996) [?].

motion so that the distance between the camera and the object is fixed while covering all viewing directions.

In the paper, they used four slabs of 90 degree coverage to form 360 degrees of azimuthal viewing. In this instance, they used a planar gantry instead of a spherical gantry [9].

Figure 1.5 highlights that the novel view synthesis occurs in two steps: First one must compute the (u, v, s, t) parameters for each image ray passing through (x, y) and secondly one must resample the radiance at those line parameters.

One begins the first step by mapping (x, y) coordinates to (u, v) ones with this transformation:

$$u = \frac{uw}{w}, \quad v = \frac{vw}{w}.$$

which normalizes the mapping (uw, vw, w) to (u, v) , reducing it to 2D. A similar procedure is used for generating the points (s, t) through the st quadrilateral [9].

In the second step, one re-samples the radiance. Which is passing the radiance of the already existing (known) points through a filter to interpolate the missing (unknown) points.

The main issue that arises here is called aliasing, which is a distance of pixels of the same point between two projected (known) camera locations. This is further exacerbated by having multiple camera locations that all share the same points in different pixels. This disparity is minimized by applying prefiltering in the form of a mipmapping algorithm [21]. Aliasing artifacts do not appear for all novel views at the same rate, thus prefiltering can be rather expensive or avoided altogether.

1.3 View-dependent Texture Mapping and Unstructured Light-Based Capture (1996-2001)

View-dependent Texture Mapping (1996)

Although standard 2D-to-3D reconstruction techniques did not exist at the time, there were four areas of research applicable to this: Camera Calibration, Stereo Correspondence, Image-Based Rendering and Structure from Motion. All of these research areas helped result in these techniques.

This technique does not focus mainly on novel view synthesis; however, it was the state of the art for reconstruction of scenes (simple 2D-to-3D reconstruction for approximate geometric shapes). The most performant at the time were image-based (using stereo algorithms) and required a lot of closely spaced camera views and would not perform well on geometric detail (bumps, corners, peaks). They were also limited by the stereo algorithm and wouldn't be able to perform better than it allowed [5].

The geometric-methods were “extremely labor intensive, typically involv[ed] surveying the site, locating and digitizing architectural plans [...]”. With their construction method, first they recreate architectural scenes (3D views of buildings). It does perform novel view synthesis in the form of their technique: View-dependent texture mapping. This is not a light-based technique like those before; one composites multiple views of a scene and blends them [5].

”Clearly, it is an attractive application to be able to explore the world's architecture unencumbered by fences, gravity, customs, or jetlag” [5].

As Figure 1.6 depicts, they mix and match the strong parts of both image-based and the geometry-based methods.

Figure 1.6: Schematic of how our hybrid approach combines geometry-based and image-based approaches to modeling and rendering architecture from photographs from [5]

“In [this] approach, a basic geometric model of the architecture is recovered [...] with an easy-to-use photogrammetric modeling system, novel views are created using view-dependent texture mapping, and additional geometric detail can be recovered automatically through stereo correspondence.” [5].

The camera is calibrated (mapping between image coordinates and directions relative to the camera is known). Also, the focus is on the “recover[y] [of] geometric models of architectural scenes” which allows them to add “constraints not typically available to structure from motion algorithms” [5], and bypass the numerical instability problem that is inherent to structure from motion.

The *correspondence* problem is the main function of structure from motion, which identifies that points in differing images represent the same point in the real world. This stereo correspondence is highly prone to errors and is difficult to do freely by computer. The approximate model here with the additional constraints (the model warps the images to eliminate unequal foreshortening and predict major occlusion before computing correspondences) enables a robust determining of the stereo correspondences [5]. The entire technique is executed in three main steps:

Photogrammetric Modelling

In specialized software (*Façade*), the user inputs digitized images and constructs a geometric model by marking the edges of the images. The software computes the “sizes and relative positions of the model components that best fit the edges marked in the photographs”. This effectively turns all major parts of the image into geometric primitives that are defined by parameters that define their size and shape (given vertex P_o , it is written in terms of width, height and length for a block as in $P_0 = (-width, -height, length)^T$). The procedure described here can be seen in Figure 1.7.

Figure 1.7: Includes a) a photograph of the Berkeley’s clock tower with marked edges in *Façade*, b) the model recovered after computation by the software c) the model reprojected to the image d) a novel, 3D view that is generated after step 2. [5]

This takes between “a few seconds [... or] a few minutes” [5].

There is a hierarchical relationship between blocks (geometric primitives), where each block has a parent or children. Their relationship is defined by a rotation matrix R and a translation vector t . both matrices have three parameters each. The user can simplify this relationship by specifying if the rotation is unconstrained, or rotation about a particular axis or fixed rotation which doesn’t require R . The same types of constraints can also be applied to R , resulting in a single parameter relationship between a block and its parent. Through these relationships $g_1(X), \dots, g_n(X)$ one can find the world coordinates and world orientation by working backwards from any block vertex $P(X)$ and block orientation $v(X)$ [5]:

$$P_w(X) = g_1(X) \dots g_n(X) P(X) \quad v_w(X) = g_1(X) \dots g_n(X) v(X)$$

Modeling in this way “greatly reduces the number of parameters that the reconstruction algorithm needs to recover” [5].

Now we have the predicted world coordinates for each vertex and edge, we get the camera’s focal point, it’s rotation and translation to transform the world coordinates of the point according to the camera space, and get the real predicted 2D line for each edge drawn.

Figure 1.8: Predicted line vs Observed edge segment; visualisation of the error. [5]

The normal vector m shown in Figure 1.8 is:

$$m = R_j(\mathbf{v} \times (\mathbf{d} - t_j))$$

where \mathbf{d} is the world-space point on the model and \mathbf{v} is the world-space direction of the edge. $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2)$ is the observed image edge, and the predicted image line is calculated by $m_x x + m_y y - m_z f = 0$. There is a minimizer function which tweaks to line up the predicted 2D lines with user-painted edges. The error of the function can be calculated as such [5]:

$$\text{Err}_i = \int_0^l h^2(s) ds = \frac{l}{3}(h_1^2 + h_1 h_2 + h_2^2) = m^T (A^T B A) m.$$

where

$$m = (m_x, m_y, m_z)^T, \quad A = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 1 \\ x_2 & y_2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \frac{l}{3(m_x^2 + m_y^2)} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1.5 \\ 1 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The final objective function O is the sum of the error terms of each correspondence.

To compute the initial estimate, one first must estimate the camera rotations R_j . For each correspondence i , the measured normal \mathbf{m}' is [5]:

$$\mathbf{m}'_i = \begin{pmatrix} x_{i1} \\ y_{i1} \\ -f \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} x_{i2} \\ y_{i2} \\ -f \end{pmatrix}$$

be the normal of the user-drawn image edge in homogeneous coordinates, and let v_i be the model-edge direction (from Eq. 2). Then

$$m_i'^T R_j v_i = 0$$

is a *linear* constraint on the entries of R_j . Solving these for all edges i gives a least-squares estimate of R_j .

Figure 1.9: Weights of the views respectively w_1 and w_2 are inversely proportional to the magnitude of angles a_1 and a_2

Then one must estimate translations and the block parameters [5]: With R_j fixed, enforce

$$m_i'^T R_j (d_i - t_j) = 0,$$

where d_i is a point on model edge i (from Eq. 1). Together with any user-defined block-alignment constraints, this again is a linear system in $\{t_j, X\}$. These define the constraints of the model parameters, the violation of these constraints will be the minimizing objective of the first objective function we'll define:

$$O_1 = \sum_i (m_i^T R_j v_i)^2, \quad v_i \in \{\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}\}.$$

We do the same for the translations, where the main aim is to have all of the points defined by $\langle v, d \rangle$ tuple should “lie on the plane with normal vector m passing through the camera center”. The minimizer function for the violation of that is [5]:

$$O_2 = \sum_i \left[m_i^T R_j (P_i(X) - t_j) \right]^2 + \left[m_i^T R_j (Q_i(X) - t_j) \right]^2.$$

Typically, both of these functions require “less than 10 iterations” to find a minimum. They are also relatively easy to compute.

The second main step in the algorithm is where the novel view synthesis happens, going back to the Digital 3D models section, this would form step 4, where one paints and adds textures to the mesh. This step is View-dependent Texture-mapping [5].

This step is described as putting “a slide projector that projects the original image onto the model” For non-convex models, some parts will fall into shadows, which are identified using an image-space shadow map algorithm (cite the guys with the actual algorithm).

For rendering the entire texture of the model, as seen from Figure 1.9 one must composite multiple image textures that will be mapped onto the model, in this case, to composite the images in the first place, the paper uses a weighting algorithm where smaller the angle between the virtual view and the actual available view, the higher the weights and the more importance those pixels receive when rendering that part of the texture of the model [5].

In the instances where an unwanted object is blocking the view to the architecture of interest, “the user may mask out the object by painting over the obstruction with a reserved color”. Then the algorithm will set those pixels’ weights in the region to be zero as a result and will ignore them.

Compared to the other novel-view synthesis methods this is the least complicated, and probably the most constrained one of the time, however, in its constrained domain it was quite potent.

The last main step of the technique is optional however helps significantly with depth perception and geometric detail ("friezes and cornices" [5]) that is not captured in the model. *Model-based stereo* employed here functions very similar to traditional stereo: given two images (the *key* and *offset*), model-based stereo computes the associated depth map for the key image by the corresponding points in the key and offset images [5].

The key difference between the two methods is that model-based stereo can take two very different images of the scene and make them appear similar, so that the mapping between the offset and the key aligns without artifacts. model-based stereo achieves this by "projecting the offset image onto the model and viewing it from the position of the key image", thus the "*warped offset*" image. This offset is much more similar to the key, and is used to find and convert correspondences between the key and itself, thus the depth of the given point can easily be calculated. Again a stereo algorithm is used to compute the depth map. Then this depth map is used to rerender the scene from novel viewpoints, and renderings are composited to each other using view-dependent texture-mapping.

Unstructured Lumigraph Rendering (2001)

This method is a generalization of the two methods we already saw, and it adapts based on situation: For "regular and planar input camera positions" [3] the algorithm behaves like the lumigraph. For "Fewer cameras and good approximate geometry" [3] the algorithm behaves like view-dependent texture mapping. Both algorithms "Interpolat[e] color values for a desired ray as some combination of input rays" [3], which is how this algorithm is able to retain their characteristics at the same time.

The point of this paper is to see, given VDTM and lumigraph were two extremes, (which perform well under their assumptions however quite poorly if the assumptions are violated) does there exist, an intermediate algorithm that will satisfy the defined goals? The unstructured lumigraph rendering, is the intermediate novel-view synthesis technique of the paper.

The goals (which no Image-based rendering model before this intermediate algorithm was able to accomplish) are as such:

Geometric proxies: geometric knowledge should be an optional input that "assist[s] in the reconstruction for a desired ray" [3]. Accurate geometric proxies allow for high quality reconstructions from a few images. This implies the VDTM part of the algorithm.

Epipole consistency: The lumigraph (light field) side of the algorithm; implies that a ray can be trivially reconstructed "when it passes through the center of projection of a source camera" [3]. Thus the ray can be used as direct output to reconstruct that pixel of the image, ensuring high quality reconstruction without requiring geometric information.

Resolution Sensitivity: Pixels of closer rays, if they align with distant camera shots (the real rays) the renderer will use them to recreate, however the reconstruction will be blurry. This is because pixels aren't the result of a single ray but an integral over a set of overlapping rays subtending a given angle, which is impacted by shot distance and focal length. This is often ignored in the lumigraph algorithm as all cameras are assumed to be the same distance from the object and have equal focal length, recreated rays and the real rays are equidistant to the object in place.

Unstructured input: An image-based algorithm should accept input images from cam-

eras in any position, not just evenly placed positions (like the lumigraph) or equidistant from the object.

Equivalent ray consistency: Through any empty region of space, the ray along it’s “line-of-sight” [3] should reconstruct every position consistently. Most algorithms look at the camera with the lowest ray angle between the image to be the one used for rendering. However, for two different viewpoints on the same ray this might mean different cameras, causing flickering upon changing the viewpoint from D_1 to D_2 while viewing the same dashed-line ray, one can observe this in Figure 1.10.

Figure 1.10: When ray angle is measured in the desired view, one can get different reconstructions for the same ray. The algorithm of Koch et al. would determine C_2 to be the closest camera for D_1 , and C_1 to be the closest camera for D_2 .

Reconstruction Color Continuity: given two rays that intersect the same point on the geometric proxy, the ray that is reconstructed later “should have a color value that is correspondingly close” [3]. The visual integrity protect the reconstruction from both temporal (flickers/abrupt color changes) and spatial (visual discontinuities) artifacts.

Minimal angular deviation: Which data cameras should be used to reconstruct a ray must be using a consistent measure of closeness. Unstructured lumigraph uses source image rays with the most similar angle to the desired ray.

Real time: The rendering algorithm should perform at “interactive rates” [3], meaning live on input.

The algorithm starts by defining and evaluating a “camera blending field” [3] on vertices in a desired image plane and “interpolating this field over the whole image”. One defines a desired ray r_d , which connects to the object/scene at point p . Then one defines r_i connecting p to the centers of each camera c_i . For each source camera (which is input) compute the angular difference between r_i and r_d :

$$angDiff(i) = \alpha_i - \alpha_d$$

as one can see below:

Figure 1.11: The angle of the k th angularly furthest camera is used as an angle threshold

To smooth the blending weight, one defines an angular threshold to only use the k best

source cameras which can be observed in Figure 1.11. This can be done by introducing a threshold as the Kth lowest angular difference source camera (achieving minimum angular deviation) [3]:

$$angThresh = angDiff(k) = \alpha_k - \alpha_d$$

Then the blend is:

$$angBlend(i) = \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{angDiff(i)}{angThresh}\right).$$

To ensure blending weights sum to 1, we normalize as:

$$normalizedAngBlend(i) = \frac{angBlend(i)}{\sum_{j=1}^k angBlend(j)}.$$

For reconstruction we need also the prediction of the degree of undersampling $resDiff(i)$, so we don't use source rays r_i that cause significant undersampling for point p (to achieve Resolution Sensitivity) [3]:

$$resDiff(i) = \max\left(0, \|p - c_i\| - \|p - d\|\right),$$

$\|p - c_i\|$ is how far the source camera i is from point p and $\|p - d\|$ is how far the desired ray is from p . If the source camera is relatively further away from p than the desired ray, so when $resDiff(i)$ is higher than 0, the sampling will be more coarse than the desired view [3].

$$angResDiff(i) = \alpha angDiff(i) + \beta resDiff(i).$$

One computes a new threshold for this undersampling issue, with the Kth lowest value of $resDiff(i)$:

$$ResThresh = resDiff(k) = \max(0, \|p - c_k\|)$$

Then converting $angThresh(i)$ and $resThresh(i)$ to a combined metric:

$$angResThresh = \alpha angThresh + \beta ResThresh$$

and computing the blend:

$$angResBlend(i) = \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{angResDiff(i)}{angResThresh}\right).$$

Both $angResBlend(i)$ and $angBlend(i)$ are piecewise, smooth linear functions that go to continuously zero (continuity).

Unstructured lumigraph also ignores rays that fall outside the field of view of the source camera, which is done by eliminating all cameras where r_i approaches the edge of the field of view of c_i

$$angResFovBlend(i) = angResBlend(i) fovBlend(i),$$

and then normalizing over all i :

$$normalizedAngResFovBlend(i) = \frac{angResFovBlend(i)}{\sum_{j=1}^k angResFovBlend(j)}.$$

The real time renderer only computes the camera blending for a discrete set of points in the image plane, then triangulates these points to interpolate the camera blending over the image [3].

The triangulation begins by introducing a single planar proxy (use of geometric proxies) for each triangle, then “project[ing] all of the vertices and edges of the proxy into the desired image plane” [3]. Then a vertex of the camera’s center is inserted to the desired image plane (maintaining epipole consistency). To further add spatial fidelity, a fixed grid of extra vertices is added onto the image plane and as constraints for the triangulation.

Then at each vertex, we compute and store a set of source cameras and their blending weights. At any given vertex, the weights sum to one. Then one interpolates these weights linearly, and renders the novel view as a set of projectively mapped triangles.

In their example, given “ m unique cameras with nonzero blending weights at three vertices of a triangle” [3], one renders the triangle m times, using the texture from each of the m cameras. The assigned texture for each vertex is assigned an alpha value equal to its blended weight at the given vertex. Then all source camera textures are projectively applied onto the rendered proxy triangle.

There is no requirement on camera layout or ordering. The paper only uses the best k source cameras for each pixel. With unstructured input, and real time rendering, this algorithm is one of the first iterations of general novel-view synthesis; where it is not dependent on niche assumptions. The algorithm performs subjectively clean using the two edges it has (VDTM and lumigraph) on many datasets: Robot, Helicopter, Knick-knacks and more [3].

Chapter 2

3D Construction before deep learning

Light-based methods were a breakthrough that showed the possibility of practical novel images, which resparked the interest in other techniques which ended up moving the past state of the art forward. Structure from Motion has a longer past, however, after the plenoptic methods there was concentrated efforts to make it more reliable and less brittle, which moved us into the novel view synthesis of late 2000s.

2.1 Structure from Motion (SfM)

A computer algorithm for reconstructing a scene from two projections

The name structure from motion comes from how mobile living organisms with eyesight map a scene (a 3D environment whether virtual or real) by looking at it from different viewpoints and connecting them in a mental scene.

This is the original structure from motion algorithm, it is “for computing the three-dimensional structure of a scene from a correlated pair of perspective projections[...]” [11].

The general algorithm requires two projections (mapping from 3D scene to image) and eight points (scene coordinates of a given point in an image) for each projection that can be located; then these projections’ relative orientations can be computed with a set of simultaneous linear equations [11].

Let P a visible point and (X_1, X_2, X_3) with (X^1, X^2, X^3) be its coordinates with respect to the two viewpoints. These coordinates are not world points (coordinates in the real world) but mappings of (x, y) in the image view of the camera and the depth (taking the camera as the 0 point of depth, and every step forward is towards positive z).

The camera image can then be defined as:

Let P be a visible point in the scene, and let (X_1, X_2, X_3) and (X'_1, X'_2, X'_3) be its three-dimensional Cartesian coordinates with respect to the two viewpoints. The ‘forward’ coordinates X_3 and X'_3 are necessarily positive [11]. The image coordinates of P in the two views may then be defined as

$$(x_1, x_2) = \left(\frac{X_1}{X_3}, \frac{X_2}{X_3} \right), \quad (x'_1, x'_2) = \left(\frac{X'_1}{X'_3}, \frac{X'_2}{X'_3} \right). \quad (2.1)$$

It is convenient to set the depth as one to ensure the camera image view and the image share the same dimensions:

$$x_3 = 1, \quad x'_3 = 1, \quad (2.2)$$

so that one can then write

$$x_\mu = \frac{X_\mu}{X_3}, \quad x'_\nu = \frac{X'_\nu}{X'_3}, \quad (\mu, \nu = 1, 2, 3). \quad (2.3)$$

In relating camera 1 and camera 2 to each other (the fundamental case), one must define translation \mathbf{T} from the position of camera 1 to camera 2, and a rotation \mathbf{R} from the camera 1's view to camera 2's view:

$$X'_\mu = R_{\mu\nu}(X_\nu - T_\nu), \quad (2.4)$$

where \mathbf{T} is an unknown translational vector and \mathbf{R} is an unknown rigid rotation matrix. The rotation \mathbf{R} preserves lengths and angles and the matrix must keep orientation and volume. Thus it satisfies the relationships:

$$\mathbf{R}\mathbf{R}^\top = \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{R}^\top\mathbf{R}, \quad \det \mathbf{R} = 1. \quad (2.5)$$

Then one must normalize the translation to use it as the scale reference for the scene.

$$\mathbf{T}^2 = \mathbf{T}_1^2 + \mathbf{T}_2^2 + \mathbf{T}_3^2 = 1. \quad (2.6)$$

Now knowing these, we are trying to simulate the coplanarity of the three vectors with linear algebra [11] (from camera 1 to P, from camera 2 to P, T) which one can observe in Figure 2.1.

Epipolar Geometry with Points Maximally Spread (0-10)

Figure 2.1: Epipolar geometry setup: two pinhole cameras C_1 and C_2 , separated by the baseline (translation) \mathbf{T} , observe a 3D point P . The viewing rays C_1P and C_2P together with \mathbf{T} span the epipolar plane; its projections in the two images are the corresponding epipolar lines. This is the configuration underlying the essential matrix $E = [\mathbf{T}]_{\times}R$.

This we can achieve by defining a new matrix Q with skew-symmetric matrix S .

$$Q = RS. \quad (2.7)$$

The matrix S is explicitly given by

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & T_3 & -T_2 \\ -T_3 & 0 & T_1 \\ T_2 & -T_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.8)$$

which can be written more compactly using the Levi-Civita symbol as

$$S_{\lambda\nu} = \varepsilon_{\lambda\nu\sigma}T_{\sigma}. \quad (2.9)$$

Here, $\varepsilon_{\lambda\nu\sigma}$ is the permutation tensor, taking values $+1$ or -1 depending on whether (λ, ν, σ) is an even or odd permutation of $(1, 2, 3)$, and 0 otherwise.

From equations (4)–(9), it follows that

$$X'_{\mu}Q_{\mu\nu}X_{\nu} = R_{\mu\kappa}(X_{\kappa} - T_{\kappa})R_{\mu\lambda}\varepsilon_{\lambda\nu\sigma}T_{\sigma}X_{\nu} = (X_{\lambda} - T_{\lambda})\varepsilon_{\lambda\nu\sigma}T_{\sigma}X_{\nu}. \quad (2.10)$$

Because $\varepsilon_{\lambda\nu\sigma}$ is antisymmetric in any pair of indices, the right-hand side vanishes, leaving

$$X'_{\mu}Q_{\mu\nu}X_{\nu} = 0. \quad (2.11)$$

Dividing by the depth coordinate $X_3X'_3$, we arrive at the purely image-based relationship

$$x'_{\mu}Q_{\mu\nu}x_{\nu} = 0, \quad (2.12)$$

which is the epipolar constraint.

Finally, for each correspondence P_i we obtain one such equation, which can be written as

$$(x'_\mu x_\nu)_i Q_{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (2.13)$$

Thus, every point correspondence contributes a linear equation in the entries of Q , and with a sufficient number of points the system can be solved [11].

If the eight equations are independent, the solution is a straightforward system [11]. Then the aim is to recover the matrices R and T from Q .

Take Q and its transpose Q^T :

$$QQ^T = 6\bar{S}RRS^T = -SS, \quad (2.14)$$

using the definition of S

$$Q_{\mu\nu}Q_{\mu\sigma} = T^2\delta_{\nu\sigma} - T_\nu T_\sigma, \quad (2.15)$$

as $T_\mu^2 = 1$:

$$Q_{\mu\nu}Q_{\mu\nu} = 5 - T^2 = 2. \quad (2.16)$$

The elements of Q is divided by $\sqrt{(1/2)\text{trace}(QQ^T)}$ to normalize, then the components of T are:

$$\hat{Q}\hat{Q}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - T_1^2 & -T_1T_2 & -T_1T_3 \\ -T_2T_1 & 1 - T_2^2 & -T_2T_3 \\ -T_3T_1 & -T_3T_2 & 1 - T_3^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.17)$$

One can now compute R , for one row of Q and R :

$$Q_\alpha = T \times R_\alpha \quad (\alpha = 1, 2, 3). \quad (2.18)$$

According to the constraints of R :

$$R_\alpha = R_\beta R_\gamma. \quad (19)$$

for indices α, β, γ with $\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = 1$. We want to express R_α in terms of T and Q_α .

By (18), R_α is orthogonal to Q_α , so it can be written as a linear combination of T and $Q_\alpha \times T$. Introduce

$$W_\alpha = Q_\alpha \times T \quad (\alpha = 1, 2, 3), \quad (20)$$

and write

$$R_\alpha = a_\alpha T + b_\alpha W_\alpha. \quad (21)$$

Substituting into (18) gives

$$Q_\alpha = T \times (a_\alpha T + b_\alpha W_\alpha) = b_\alpha (T \times W_\alpha). \quad (22)$$

Since T is a unit vector,

$$T \times W_\alpha = T \times (Q_\alpha \times T) = Q_\alpha, \quad (23)$$

hence

$$b_\alpha = 1. \quad (24)$$

From (19), when $\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = 1$ we get

$$a_\alpha T + W_\alpha = (a_\beta T + W_\beta) \times (a_\gamma T + W_\gamma) = a_\beta Q_\gamma - a_\gamma Q_\beta + W_\beta \times W_\gamma. \quad (25)$$

In (25), W_α , Q_β , and Q_γ are all orthogonal to T , while $W_\beta \times W_\gamma$ is, by (20), a multiple of T . Therefore the first term on the left equals the last term on the right:

$$a_\alpha T = W_\beta \times W_\gamma, \quad (26)$$

and (21) becomes

$$R_\alpha = W_\alpha + W_\beta \times W_\gamma. \quad (27)$$

Having found the vector T and the three rows of the matrix R , we can now obtain the three-dimensional coordinates X'_μ as follows. By (4),

$$X'_\mu = R_{\mu\nu} (X_\nu - T_\nu).$$

from which it follows that

$$x'_i = \frac{X'_1}{X'_3} = \frac{R_{1\nu} (X_\nu - T_\nu)}{R_{3\nu} (X_\nu - T_\nu)}. \quad (28)$$

Introducing the vectors

$$X = (X_1, X_2, X_3), \quad x = (x_1, x_2, 1), \quad (29)$$

we may write equation (28) in terms of the rows R_α of the matrix R :

$$x'_i = \frac{R_1 \cdot (X - T)}{R_3 \cdot (X - T)} = \frac{R_1 \cdot \left(x - \frac{T}{X_3}\right)}{R_3 \cdot \left(x - \frac{T}{X_3}\right)}. \quad (30)$$

from which it follows that

$$X_3 = \frac{(R_1 - x'_i R_3) \cdot T}{(R_1 - x'_i R_3) \cdot x}. \quad (31)$$

The other unprimed coordinates are then given by equation (3) as

$$X_1 = x_1 X_3, \quad X_2 = x_2 X_3, \quad (32)$$

and the primed coordinates are finally obtained from equation (4).

$$X' = R(X - T). \quad (32)$$

This algorithm, however simple, has brittle points: given seven points that lie in a plane, or four points in a straight line, the configuration will be degenerate [11]. Configuration will also be degenerate, if six of the points in the shape of a hexagon, or eight points in the shape of a cube [11].

This algorithm gave way to sparse input being able to represent a 3D scene, compared to dense representations required in plenoptic functions, theoretically. Even with subsequent papers showing practical applications, it was performed mainly on carefully calibrated datasets [11].

Photo Tourism: Exploring Photo Collections in 3D

This is the first paper to execute structure from motion on randomly selected photos from the Internet. It is an app with a 3D interface to explore a scene in 3D. Using the interface, one is able to “fly around popular world sites in 3D by morphing between photos” [19].

This paper uses a modification of the Brown and Lowe [2005 REFERENCE] structure from motion algorithm to create a 3D environment from sparse images. These include: “Initializing new cameras using pose estimation, to help avoid local minima; a different heuristic for selecting the initial two images for SfM; checking that reconstructed points are well-conditioned before adding them to the scene; and using focal length information from EXIF tags” [19].

The paper also uses novel view synthesis in conjunction with the sparse 3D representation, however not to “synthesize a photo-realistic view of the world from all viewpoints[...] but to browse a specific collection of photographs in a 3D spatial context” [19]. They don’t use plenoptic functions or view interpolations, their technique is most similar to the MovieMap technique that was the “forerunner to this field” [19] for novel view synthesis, only “in an improved and generalized form” [19].

The general technique follows as such: once the images are uploaded, objects clearly defined in the image have their position detected which are called feature points. Then these feature points are matched between pairs of images, then one runs an iterative modified SfM to recover the camera parameters (the 3D space). These relative (x, y, z) positions obtained are then mapped onto an overhead map, which is a geo-referenced image of the absolute transformation, position and scale of objects to map the SfM representation to [19].

Keypoint detection is performed with the SIFT algorithm, which also writes a description of the keypoint [12]. Once they are established, they are matched based on their keypoint descriptors, using the “approximate nearest neighbors package of Arya” [1] they then run RANSAC (random sample consensus): repeatedly estimate the pair’s epipolar geometry (the fundamental matrix via the eight-point method), keep pairs that fit it, and throw out outliers; if there aren’t enough good matches “less than twenty” [19], they discard that photo pair. Then they “organize the matches into tracks, where a track is a connected set of matching keypoints across images” [19] Given a track there can only be one distinctive keypoint (the same object that is used to map multiple images along one track can’t appear twice in the same image). Thus tracks that have images with multiple keypoints are removed, and tracks that have multiple images containing the same keypoint that don’t have repeat distinctive keypoints are kept [19].

For each track then a 3D representation is recovered: the initial conditions for the parameters (x, y, z) of each track’s projections are framed as a “non-linear least squares problem” [19] of the difference between the unknown real positions of each track and their projections. This is solved using Levenberg-Marquardt [15] which find a local minima and set the initial positions accordingly for the SfM to start [19].

SfM’s goal here is to map the 3D plane position of each pairs of images incrementally, and modify the mapping with each subsequent camera accordingly. The image pairs are that have the largest number of matches are chosen first, subject “to the condition that those matches cannot be well-modeled by a single homography” [19] in which case the camera mapping does not have depth; it is a 3D degenerate mapping that has the attributes of a 2D image. This process is repeated with each new camera, and each cam-

era’s initial parameters are defined using “direct linear transform [7] inside a RANSAC procedure” [19]. The DLT is used also to estimate a parameter matrix K , which is used to initialize the focal length of the new camera using EXIF tags. Finally tracks that belong to the new camera are added to optimize. A track in this condition is added only if it is also observed by at least one other camera and if the triangulation gives a well-conditioned estimate of its location. This is repeated until there is no possible new 3D position of a track that can be added to a camera (all are exhausted). After this there is a “post-processing step to detect 3d line segments in the scene using a line segment reconstruction technique [16]” [19].

To increase speed, they have modified this algorithm: “After every run of the optimization, we detect outlier tracks that contain at least one keypoint with a high reprojection error, and remove these tracks” [19]. They repeat this each run until no outliers are detected at the start of the next run. They also add multiple cameras to the optimization instead of just one, they order cameras in accordance to: “the greatest number of matches, M , to existing 3D points, then add any camera with at least $0.75M$ matches to existing points” [19].

The final step of the algorithm is the overhead mapping using a geo-referenced image to determine absolute coordinates. This step is optional. A transformation to achieve this can be found by estimating an “up’ or gravity vector” [19] to reduce the transformation to 2D, or the transformation can be recovered from gps tags (if available) attached to a few of the images in existing tracks and adding their positions as constraints to the SfM optimization.

They represent the reconstructed scene used in the photo exploration tool with the following elements:

- A set of 3D points $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$. Each point has a 3D position and a color, where the color is taken from one of the images where the point is visible.
- A set of cameras $\mathcal{C} = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$. Each camera C_j includes its image I_j , rotation R_j , translation t_j , and focal length f_j .
- A mapping between cameras and the points they see. For a camera c , the set $\text{Points}(c)$ is the subset of \mathcal{P} that camera c observes.
- A set of 3D line segments $\mathcal{L} = \{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_m\}$ and a mapping Lines between cameras and the line segments they observe.

Despite the small modifications that allow for rendering of whole 3D spaces, this algorithm requires high levels of compute: “the total running time of the SfM [...] ranged from a few hours [...] to about two weeks” [19]. The modified SfM also suffers in accuracy due to being somewhat dependent on strong initial (x, y, z) camera positions: “Our SfM procedure is also not guaranteed to produce a metric scene reconstruction without ground points” [19].

The next paper allowed the structure from motion representations to become dense and include finer details. Structure from motion then became a stable in preprocessing images in order to recover camera positions and the general 3D geometry of the scene. This new technique is the next step that involves fleshing out the sparse geometry from structure from motion with stereo matching, called Multi-view Stereo [17].

2.2 SfM + Multi-View Stereo (SOTA pre-deep-learning)

Structure from Motion solves for the calibrated cameras R_i, T_i to create a sparse point cloud. Once these camera positions are fixed. Multi-view stereo uses these cameras to estimate the depth for every pixel of images taken from the fixed cameras. A candidate depth for a given reference pixel $\mathbf{p} = (x_1, x_2, 1)$ is $d > 0$. With the knowledge of this depth, one can approximate the world position of the pixel (X_d):

$$X(d) = C_r + d R_r^\top \tilde{p}, \quad C_r = -R_r^\top T_r, \quad \tilde{x}_i(d) \sim K_i(R_i X(d) + T_i).$$

The aim is not to solve for the depth but to minimize the the photometric cost (this minimization is where MVS algorithms differ from each other). Project this into a view i :

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i(d) \sim K_i(R_i X(d) + T_i), \quad \mathbf{x}_i(d) = \Pi(K_i(R_i X(d) + T_i)),$$

C_r is the center point of the camera. R and T being the translations and rotation (extrinsic parameters) of the camera. where the perspective division operator is:

$$\Pi([u, v, w]^\top) = \left(\frac{u}{w}, \frac{v}{w} \right).$$

The equation for the photometric cost C for a patch $N(p)$:

$$C(\mathbf{p}, d) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{p})|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{p})} \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{p})} \ell(I_r(\mathbf{q}) - I_i(\mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{q}; d))).$$

where $\mathcal{S}(p)$ being the set of source views that include the reference pixel p and function $\ell()$ being the pixel wise loss due to inaccurate depth and $w_i(\mathbf{q}; d)$ being the warped position of another reference pixel \mathbf{q} . Then one can evaluate the depth estimate:

$$d^*(\mathbf{p}) = \arg \min_{d>0} C(\mathbf{p}, d).$$

d^* can be computed with many methods, one of them being discrete search: One chooses a set of candidate depths d_k . Then for each d_k one warps the source images via the camera geometry (which means manually referring to the pixel p in the source image for which you are trying to optimize depth). The one chooses the most suitable depth:

$$d^*(\mathbf{p}) = \arg \min_{d>0} C(\mathbf{p}, d_k).$$

This is the simplest form of multi-view stereo. There are four categories of MVS according to their object models: voxel-based: establishes a bounding box grid on the scene. The accuracy of the algorithm is dependent on the resolution of the established grid. Deformable polygonal mesh approaches: depend on an optimal visual hull model to initialize an optimization process. Multiple depth map approaches: require fusing individual depth maps of the taken images to form a 3D model. Patch-based methods: represent scene surfaces by collections of small patches. These work effectively however, to turn into a mesh (which is a digital rendered 3D object) one requires a postprocessing step.

Voxel and polygonal mesh methods work very good for singular object images, as it is easier to estimate a bounding box for the object. Multiple depth map method works better for scenes that involve vegetation, buildings, and slightly denser representations.

For each of the objects in the view one does not possess full coverage within the shot, thus local depth estimations can achieve a stronger accuracy. For crowded scenes, patch based methods work best as when objects are in front of other objects and obstructing the view partially, patch based methods can still create consistent parts of each object while ignoring the outliers (the boundary points between objects). Still these scenes are difficult to create novel views for.

COLMAP:

Structure-from-Motion Revisited

This is the industry standard technique that was also used to generate datasets for the deep-learning based models, because it is fully open-sourced under the name *COLMAP*. It is a variation of Structure-from-motion and Multi-view Stereo. This paper refers only to structure from motion part.

The modified technique starts with “Correspondence Search” [18] which finds scene overlap in the input Images $\mathbf{I} = \{I_i | i = 1 \dots N_I\}$ ” The idea is to find “a set of geometrically verified image pairs” [18] \mathcal{C} and “a graph of image projections” [18] per point.

one defines sets of local features for each image I_i at location x_j by:

$$\mathcal{F}_i = \{(\mathbf{x}_j, f_j) \mid j = 1 \dots N_{F_i}\}.$$

These features are “invariant under radiometric and geometric changes” [18] to enhance their unique representation in SfM. The next step is matching. SfM tries to pair images if they see the “same scene part” [18] depending on the features \mathcal{F}_i . The simplest method tries every image pair for scene overlap, by trying every feature of image I_a with each feature of image I_b , which results in

$$O(N_I^2 N_{F_i}^2).$$

One finds a set of overlapping pairs[18]:

$$\mathcal{C} = \{\{I_a, I_b\} \mid I_a, I_b \in \mathcal{I}, a < b\}.$$

Then one proceeds with geometric verification of the corresponding features in each image pair. One defines a homography \mathbf{H} and epipolar geometry matrices \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{F} . If one of these transformation matrices “maps sufficient number of features between image pairs, then the pair is geometrically verified” [18]. The next stage is incremental reconstruction. This takes as input the scene graph (a graph with images as nodes and verified image pairs as edges). One initializes from a “carefully selected two-view reconstruction” [18] as without a strong initial pair the reconstruction may never reach an acceptable accuracy [18]. A dense location (one with many image-pairs overlapping over similar features) “results in a more robust and accurate reconstruction” [18], however sparser locations have “lower runtimes” [18] as there is less redundancy of features. This process results in the “reconstructed scene” [18] in a set of points $X = \{X_k \in R^3 \mid k = 1 \dots N_X\}$. Then one performs image registration: adding and registering new images to the reconstructed scene by solving the Perspective-n-Point (PnP) problem [18]. One estimates the pose \mathbf{P}_c . The set of registered images \mathcal{P} is extended by the pose \mathbf{P}_c . After adding new registered images to the scene, one observes existing scene points to create the parallax, and to increase the stability of overlapping views (redundancy) between new images

and old registered images. This computation is called triangulation, and it also enables more new images to be registered [18]. The final step is bundle adjustment. “Image registration and triangulation are separate procedures, even though their products are highly correlated” [18]. The newly added camera poses may have slight errors in their transformation and rotation, which would create inaccurate triangulations and vice-versa. The opposite is also true however: “additional triangulations may improve the initial camera pose through increased redundancy” [18]. Bundle adjustment refines these two products by minimizing the reprojection error E with a function π that “projects scene points to an image space” [18] and a loss function \sqrt{j} that lowers the weight of outliers.

$$E = \sum_j \rho_j (\|\pi(P_c, X_k) - x_j\|_2^2).$$

There are two main types of algorithms for BA (bundle adjustment): exact step and inexact step algorithms: the former requires higher levels of compute as it solves the system by storing it as a matrix $\mathcal{O}(N_P^2)$ or $\mathcal{O}(N_P^3)$ while the latter approximates the system by iterating on it through following gradients. This paper uses an inexact step algorithm to be able to work with large data of “Internet Photos” [18].

This was the entire process; COLMAP introduces the fact that many registrable images that would improve redundancy and provide a denser graph are often ignored by systems. They improve upon four key points of the process: geometric verification, incremental reconstruction, triangulation and bundle adjustment [18].

The first improvement is geometric verification: they establish a fundamental matrix that describes epipolar geometry between two views. Then they filter pairs of images by ensuring the number of inliers supporting the fundamental matrix, N_F , surpasses a determined threshold. Then they estimate a homography and count its inliers N_H . If this inequality does not hold, the scene is classified as a non-planar environment captured by a moving camera:

$$\frac{N_H}{N_F} < \epsilon_{HF}. \quad (2.19)$$

For already calibrated images one can run an additional check to verify correct calibration, given the following holds for the number of essential matrix inliers N_E :

$$\frac{N_E}{N_F} > \epsilon_{EF}. \quad (2.20)$$

One also needs to filter for unique things in “Internet images” [18] such as “watermarks, timestamps and frames (WTFs)” [18] which can create false common features between unrelated images. Image pairs flagged as WTFs given their similarity transformation N_S are rejected from the pair set:

$$\frac{N_S}{N_F} > \epsilon_{SF} \quad \vee \quad \frac{N_S}{N_E} > \epsilon_{SE}, \quad (2.21)$$

$$\frac{N_S}{N_F} > \epsilon_{SF} \quad \vee \quad \frac{N_S}{N_E} > \epsilon_{SE}. \quad (2.22)$$

All validated image points are annotated with their determined model type “(general, panoramic, planar)” and the optimal inlier set.

The second improvement is next best view selection. Here the authors propose a multi-resolution scoring scheme: They discretize images into a multi-level pyramid of

grids. At each level l , the image is partitioned into a grid of $K_l \times K_l$ cells, then they double the resolution at every progressing level.

$$K_l = 2^l. \quad (2.23)$$

They score these views by labeling each cell in the grid as empty or full. These states change when any triangulated point projects within a cell's boundaries. The score S_i for an image i is the total of full cells across all levels of the pyramid. Each cell contributes a weight of w_l once [18]:

$$w_l = K_l^2. \quad (2.24)$$

Thus higher grid levels contribute more significantly to the overall score, and the total for an image becomes:

$$S_i = \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{c=1}^{K_l^2} w_l \cdot I_{\text{full}}(c, l), \quad (2.25)$$

where $I_{\text{full}}(c, l)$ is an indicator function equal to 1 if cell c at level l is full. This view selection ensures an image scores higher with numerous visible points that are uniformly spread across the image, which sets up a strong configuration for PnP solving after. The third improvement is on triangulation. The authors employ a multi-view method that solves triangulation as a RANSAC problem. Given a feature track $\mathcal{T} = \{T_n \mid n = 1 \dots N_T\}$ (set of normalized image observations), and a camera pose P_n , they seek a consensus set. The minimal sample of this can be two views that triangulate X_{ab}

$$\mathbf{X}_{ab} \sim \tau(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_a, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_b, \mathbf{P}_a, \mathbf{P}_b) \quad \text{with} \quad a \neq b. \quad (2.26)$$

A hypothesized point is well conditioned if it has a sufficient triangulation angle α between observing cameras [18]:

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{(\mathbf{t}a - \mathbf{X}_{ab}) \cdot (\mathbf{t}b - \mathbf{X}_{ab})}{\|\mathbf{t}a - \mathbf{X}_{ab}\|_2 \cdot \|\mathbf{t}b - \mathbf{X}_{ab}\|_2}, \quad (2.27)$$

and if it has positive depth (cheirality constraint) [18] for all views in its consensus set. The depth d_n for camera P_n is:

$$d_n = [p_{31} \quad p_{32} \quad p_{33} \quad p_{34}] \cdot [\mathbf{X}_{ab}^T \quad 1]^T. \quad (2.28)$$

Thus the measurement \mathcal{T}_n is added to the consensus set given:

$$e_n = \left\| \bar{\mathbf{x}}_n - \begin{bmatrix} x'/z' \\ y'/z' \end{bmatrix} \right\|_2 \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{bmatrix} = P_n \begin{bmatrix} X_{ab} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.29)$$

This implementation achieves unique minimal pairs. It is also able to recover from contaminated tracks through reducing the largest consensus set, running the RANSAC on the remaining points and terminating when no set of size three or larger can be found.

The last improvement is on bundle adjustment. After each image registration, an additional local BA step is performed to optimize only on the closest cameras and address local errors before global BA. Global BA is computationally expensive, and this local BA step reduces the run time to linear run time. The authors also introduce a post-global-BA re-triangulation step. This step triangulates points from tracks that possess inaccurate

poses that were enhanced by global BA to increase redundancy of views. Then the authors filter observations that still possess a high reprojection error. This is repeated until the global BA converges [18]. This has strong net positive impact on the accuracy and robustness of the 3D geometry of the scene that is computed, however there is one more improvement on BA to combat the fact that it is very computationally challenging: Clustering redundant cameras. This algorithm pairs cameras into groups by a single shared pose: they are divided into affected (new or with high error) and unaffected sets. Then one finds highly overlapping image sets from any set of large unaffected cameras [18]: $\mathcal{G} = G_r \mid r = 1 \dots N_G$ Similarity of images a and b is measured by a binary visibility vector \mathbf{v}_i , that maps the images to the points they see N_X :

$$V_{ab} = \frac{|\mathbf{v}_a \wedge \mathbf{v}_b|}{|\mathbf{v}_a \vee \mathbf{v}_b|}. \quad (2.30)$$

Then a greedy algorithm groups images based on similarity $V_{ab} > V_{\min}$, then a group pose is calculated based on the projection matrix for each image \mathbf{P}_c and a group transform $\mathbf{G}_r \in \text{SE}(3)$:

$$\mathbf{P}_{cr} = \mathbf{P}_c \mathbf{G}_r. \quad (2.31)$$

The BA cost function of these grouped images is:

$$E_g = \sum_j \rho_j (|\pi_g(\mathbf{G}_r, \mathbf{P}_c, \mathbf{X}_k) - \mathbf{x}_j|_2^2). \quad (2.32)$$

Thus many unaffected cameras that share a singular image collapse into a single variable for the global BA. The overall cost \bar{E} for the complete BA problem then becomes the sum of this grouped cost E_g and the standard cost for affected cameras.

This was the zenith point of the structure from motion algorithm, and the next paper is the second step of dense 3D geometry creation (mesh creation: 2D to 3D reconstruction), which is a variant of the multi-view stereo algorithm [17].

Pixelwise View Selection for Unstructured Multi-View Stereo

This part improves upon multi-view stereo in six core ways. Each of which will be expanded upon, however requires the introduction of a framework “Joint View Selection and Depth Estimation”: This is a method that takes a set of source images $\mathbf{X}^{\text{src}} = \{X^m \mid m = 1 \dots M\}$. then “estimates the depth θ_l ” of a given pixel in a reference image X^{ref} . This is achieved by defining a set of binary occlusion indicators $Z_l^m \in 0, 1$ for each source image m . If an occlusion indicator is on: $Z_l^m = 1$, then one can include the source patch for depth estimation. The probability of observing a source path given the occlusion state and the hypothesised depth is [17]:

$$P(X_l^m | Z_l^m, \theta_l) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{NA} \exp\left(-\frac{(1-\rho_l^m(\theta_l))^2}{2\sigma_p^2}\right) & , \text{if } Z_l^m = 1 \\ \frac{1}{N} \mathcal{U} & \end{cases}. \quad (2.33)$$

The normalized cross-correlation (NCC) ρ_l^m is defined for the warped source patch and the reference patch, on an assumed hypothesis depth θ_l . This model measures color similarity for visible patches with a uniform distribution \mathcal{U} for occluded patches. The model promotes smooth occlusion with a markov chain between neighbouring pixels [17]:

$$P(Z_l^m | Z_{l-1}^m) = (\gamma \quad 1 - \gamma \quad 1 - \gamma \quad \gamma). \quad (2.34)$$

From now on one can see the statistical transformation of the state of the art into the deep learning techniques. Inference is performed over the chain for all possible depths and occlusion indicators to recover the posterior distribution $P(Z, \theta|X)$. However performing direct Inference isn't intractable, thus a "generalized expectation maximization" algorithm is employed. This is compromised of two steps: E-step: With depths θ fixed, infer the occlusion indicators $q(Z) \approx P(Z|X, \theta)$ using the forward-backward algorithm for each hidden Markov chain. Then the M-step: after fixing the occlusion indicators, one optimizes the depths θ . This is performed by a PatchMatch-inspired strategy that propagates good hypotheses spatially [17].

The optimal depth from this approach minimizes the expected photometric error over all source images, with probability of being visible $P_l(m)$ as weights:

$$\theta_l^{\text{opt}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta_l} \sum m = 1^M P_l(m)(1 - \rho_l^m(\theta_l^*)). \quad (2.35)$$

One uses a monte carlo approximation to mitigate the high computational cost of this technique. Only the best subset of source images S (containing the most information) is used to optimize the depth:

$$\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{opt}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta_l} \theta_l^* l \frac{1}{|S|} \sum m \in S (1 - \rho_l^m(\theta_l^*)). \quad (2.36)$$

The paper builds off of their past technique with improvements: the old frameworks established a homography for patch warping that created artifacts on oblique surfaces. The authors establish an algorithm that approximates depth θ_l and a surface normal $\mathbf{n}_l \in R^3$ to define slanted planes for each pixel. Then one can define a homography for warping a patch from X^{ref} to X^{src} :

$$\mathbf{H}_l = \mathbf{K}^m (\mathbf{R}^m - d_l^{-1} \mathbf{t}^m \mathbf{n}_l^T) \mathbf{K}^{-1}. \quad (2.37)$$

$\mathbf{p}_l = \theta_l \mathbf{K}^{-1} \mathbf{x}_l$ is the 3D point and $d_l = \mathbf{n}_l^T \mathbf{p}_l$ is the orthogonal distance to the point. This variant of the homography model represents all surfaces accurately. Optimal depth and normal can be found by jointly minimizing the two (as did the old framework) [17]:

$$(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{opt}}, \hat{\mathbf{n}}_l^{\text{opt}}) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l} \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{m \in S} (1 - \rho_l^m(\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l)). \quad (2.38)$$

The local slanted plane adds additional complexity to the search space, and to maintain the computational costs, the authors exploit the patch surface's first-order smoothness by reusing the depth of an individual pixel's slanted plane θ_{l-1}^{pp} in neighboring pixels (a variation of PatchMatch), which is repeated at each step that combines local perturbations and each neighbor's local slanted planes [17]:

$$(\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l), (\theta_l - 1^{\text{pp}}, \mathbf{n}_{l-1}), (\theta_l^{\text{md}}, \mathbf{n}_l), (\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l^{\text{md}}), (\theta_l^{\text{md}}, \mathbf{n}_l^{\text{md}}), (\theta_l^{\text{prt}}, \mathbf{n}_l), (\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l^{\text{prt}}) \quad (2.39)$$

here θ_l^{md} and \mathbf{n}_l^{md} are random samples and $\theta_l^{\text{prt}} = (1 \pm \epsilon)\theta_l$ and $\mathbf{n}_l^{\text{prt}} = \mathbf{R}\epsilon\mathbf{n}_l$ are perturbations of the best estimate.

The next improvement step is for most informative view selection for unstructured imagery. To refuse the degenerate configurations the old framework was susceptible to include in the geometry it fleshes out, the authors inject the requirements of information from a view into the inference, in a similar fashion to an attention layer in a transformer block: they require for every pixel the geometric priors: Triangulation, Resolution and

Incident. The triangulation prior promotes images with high depth information, the triangulation angle α_l^m is used to measure reconstruction stability, and the likelihood function that measures it penalizes angles below $\bar{\alpha}$ [17]:

$$P(\alpha_l^m) = 1 - \frac{(\min(\alpha_l^m, \bar{\alpha}) - \bar{\alpha})^2}{\bar{\alpha}^2}. \quad (2.40)$$

The resolution prior matches the size and shape of shared patches between source and reference, and penalizes relative patch ratio β_l^m that is further from 1.

$$P(\beta_l^m) = \min(\beta_l^m, (\beta_l^m)^{-1}). \quad (2.41)$$

The incident prior is there to create a visibility constraint: the prior favors only cameras that are located in the positive half-space defined by the local surface plane with normal \mathbf{n}_l . The incident angle κ_l^m between the surface normal and the viewing ray must be less than 90° [17]:

$$P(\kappa_l^m) = \exp\left(-\frac{\kappa_l^m}{2\sigma_\kappa^2}\right). \quad (2.42)$$

These are integrated into the monte carlo view sampling distribution. This helps further optimize over additional parameters on top of minimizing photometric occlusion probability from occlusion indicators to favor dense, similar resolution, redundant views with observable depth information, significantly boosting performance in unstructured datasets. An additional improvement over view selection is adding a temporal smoothness factor. This helps to reduce oscillations caused by alternating propagation directions during inference. The “temporal state-transition” [17] is:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{state in the previous iteration } t \\ s \end{array} P(Z_{l,t}^m | Z_{l,t-1}^m) = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_t & 1 - \lambda_t \\ 1 - \lambda_t & \lambda_t \end{pmatrix},$$

Larger λ_t “enforces greater temporal smoothness”, then, to increase smoothness, as $Z_{l,t}^m$ approaches optimal solution: $t = 1 \dots T$, one adaptively increases the lambda: $\lambda_t = \frac{t}{2T} + 0.5$. Then one can build the evolution for the “two-state transitions [which] are jointly modeled as” [17]:

$$P(Z_{l,t}^m | Z_{l-1,t}^m, Z_{l,t-1}^m) = P(Z_{l,t}^m | Z_{l-1,t}^m) P(Z_{l,t}^m | Z_{l,t-1}^m).$$

The next improvement is in photometric consistency. The NCC algorithm employed in the previous framework is susceptible to producing “blurred depth discontinuities” [17], to reduce these artifacts one can adapt a “bilaterally weighted adaptation of NCC” [17]. The authors compute the color similarity between a reference patch w_l at x_l and a source patch w_l^m at x_l^m as:

$$\rho_l^m = \frac{\text{cov}_w(\mathbf{w}_l, \mathbf{w}_l^m)}{\sqrt{\text{cov}_w(\mathbf{w}_l, \mathbf{w}_l) \text{cov}_w(\mathbf{w}_l^m, \mathbf{w}_l^m)}},$$

” where

$$\text{cov}_w(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = E_w(\mathbf{x} - E_w(\mathbf{x})) E_w(\mathbf{y} - E_w(\mathbf{y})),$$

is the weighted covariance and $E_w(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_i w_i x_i / \sum_i w_i$ is the weighted average” [17]. The weight $w_i = \exp(-\frac{\Delta g_i}{2\sigma_g^2} - \frac{\Delta x_i}{2\sigma_x^2})$ indicates the probability of pixel i being in the same plane as the center pixel at l , where $\Delta g_i = |g_i - g_l|$ is the color distance and $\Delta x_i = \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_l\|$

is the spatial distance. The fourth improvement is on geometric consistency. This is normally a post-processing step in order to remove artifacts such as “noise, ambiguities, occlusions, etc” [17]. The authors employ a multi-view geometric consistency constraints to increase “both the completeness and accuracy.” [17]. As each ambiguity is unique to certain patch or an object, they use multiple views that share space and compute “forward-backward reprojection error $\psi_l^m = \|x_l - H_l^m H_l x_l\|$ where H_l^m denotes the projective backward transformation from source to the reference image” [17]. The point is that the estimated depths and normals are accurate given that the reprojection error ψ_l^m is small [17]. “To handle occlusion in the source image,” one uses a geometric cost $\xi_l^m = 1 - \rho_l^m + \eta \min(\psi_l^m, \psi_{\max})$ using $\eta = 0.5$. One can now compute the optimal depth and normal with: $(\hat{\theta}_l^{\text{opt}}, \hat{\mathbf{n}}_l^{\text{opt}}) = \underset{\theta_l^*, \mathbf{n}_l^*}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{m \in S} \xi_l^m(\theta_l^*, \mathbf{n}_l^*)$. where $P(\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l | \theta_l^m, \mathbf{n}_l^m)$ is the

geometric consistency term. Now the authors propose how the individual terms are integrated into the “optimization framework”. The “joint likelihood function” stacking everything is “ $P(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{N}) = \prod_{l=1}^L \prod_{m=1}^M [P(Z_{l,t}^m | Z_{l,t-1}^m, Z_{l,t-1}^m) P(X_l^m | Z_l^m, \theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l) P(\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l | \theta_l^m, \mathbf{n}_l^m)]$,”

where \mathbf{X} are the input images, \mathbf{Z} are occlusion indicators, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are the depths, and the normals are \mathbf{N} . The equation consists of the spatial smoothness term: $P(Z^m | Z^{m-1})$ that enforces coherent occlusion maps, the photometric consistency term: $P(X^m | Z^m, \theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l)$ which is computed using bilateral NCC and slanted homographies, and geometric consistency term $P(\theta_l, \mathbf{n}_l | \theta_l^m, \mathbf{n}_l^m)$ that uses many views to improve consistency. For inference to be possible, “we employ variational inference” to approximate $P(\mathbf{Z}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{N} | \mathbf{X})$ with:

$$q(\mathbf{Z}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{N}) = q(\mathbf{Z})q(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{N}). \quad (2.43)$$

The GEM algorithm solves this optimization iteratively with E-steps and M-steps:

$$q(Z^m | l) = \frac{1}{A} \overrightarrow{m}(Z^m | l) \overleftarrow{m}(Z_l^m), \quad (2.44)$$

with forward and backward messages defined recursively:

$$\overrightarrow{m}^{(Z^m | Z^{m-1})} = P(X^m | Z^m, \theta_{l+1}, \mathbf{n}_{l+1}) \sum_{Z^{m-1}} \overrightarrow{m}^{(Z^{m-1} | Z^{m-2})} P(Z^m | Z^{m-1}), \quad (2.45)$$

$$\overleftarrow{m}^{(Z^m | Z^{m+1})} = \sum_{Z^{m+1}} \overleftarrow{m}^{(Z^{m+1} | Z^{m+2})} P(X^m | Z^m, \theta_{l+1}, \mathbf{n}_{l+1}) P(Z^m | Z^{m+1}). \quad (2.46)$$

The optimization integration thus first initializes depths and normals for each image independently, then achieves geometric refinement through “coordinate descent optimization to infer geometrically consistent depths and normals [...] by [...] E and M step in both stages using row- and column- wise propagation” [17].

Filtering and fusion are the final improvements on this technique. This is the second step in the post-processing stage that filters contaminated views and fuses the consistent views into a singular dense point cloud. This starts from the a hypothesised rule: “an inlier observation should be both photometrically and geometrically stable with support from multiple views.” [17]. Photometric stability can be observed from the set of views where the probability of being non-occluded exceeds threshold:

$$\mathcal{S}^{\text{pho}} l = x^m l \mid q(Z^m | l) > \bar{q}_Z, \quad (2.47)$$

geometric stability is achieved by satisfying triangulation ($q(\alpha^{ml})$), resolution ($q(\beta^{ml})$) and incident angle ($q(\kappa^{ml})$) prior thresholds:

$$\mathcal{S}^{\text{geo}l} = x^{ml} \mid q(\alpha^{ml}) \geq \bar{q}\alpha, q(\beta^{ml}) \geq \bar{q}\beta, q(\kappa^{ml}) > \bar{q}\kappa, \psi^{ml} < \psi_{\text{max}}. \quad (2.48)$$

The reprojection error constraint ($\psi^{ml} < \psi_{\text{max}}$): The effective set is the intersection: $\mathcal{S}l = \mathcal{S}^{\text{pho}l} \cap \mathcal{S}^{\text{geo}l}$. The fusion step matches groups in the collection of all supported observations which is viewed as a graph, with nodes as pixels and edges as transformations between consistent pixels. Fusion finds maximal clusters of mutually consistent nodes: First a new cluster is seeded with the highest support node $|\mathcal{S}|$. Then a 3D point \mathbf{p}_0 and a normal \mathbf{n}_0 are projected. Then the connected nodes are checked to satisfy: depth consistency $\theta_i : \frac{|\hat{\theta}_0 - \theta_i|}{\hat{\theta}_0} < \epsilon_\theta$ normal consistency: $1 - \mathbf{n}_0^T \mathbf{n}_i < \epsilon_n$ and reprojection error of \mathbf{p}_0 must be $\psi_i < \psi$. Finally clusters with at least three elements are fused. The final point is the median location and mean normal of all cluster members. This process iterates until the graph of suitable pixels are emptied, forming the dense 3D point cloud clusters [17].

The structure from motion algorithm was used as a high quality dataset provider for the deep-learning methods to come after, and COLMAP was unrivaled in accuracy until a certain technique was established, which is the topic of the next chapter.

Chapter 3

Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) and Gaussian Splatting

3.1 NeRF: Representing Scenes as Neural Radiance Fields

This paper is not the first nor the last attempt of deep learning for novel view synthesis and 3D reconstruction, however it was the first proof that deep learning methods can be accurate on unstructured data sets with acceptable efficiency and relatively high accuracy.

NeRF, Neural Radiance Field, is a model that optimizes a plenoptic volumetric scene function with “a sparse set of input views” [14]. NeRF comes full circle: plenoptic functions showed proof that it is possible to synthesize acceptable novel views in the classical way with, which NeRF does for deep learning models [14].

NeRF represents a static scene as a “continuous 5D function that outputs the radiance emitted in each direction (θ, ϕ) at each point (x, y, z) in space, and a density at each point which acts like a differential opacity controlling how much radiance is accumulated by a ray passing through (x, y, z) ”. It is a full lumigraph plenoptic function, that is enhanced by a “fully-connected [multi-layer perceptron]” [14].

One must dwell further into the multi-layer perceptron, as the plenoptic method has been explained. The MLP layer takes as input the “single continuous 5D coordinate (spatial location (x, y, z) and viewing direction (θ, ϕ) ” [14] and outputs a “volume density $[\sigma]$ and view-dependent emitted radiance $[c = (r, g, b)]$ ” [14]. These can be computed with the expected color $C(r)$ being $C(r) = \int_{t_n}^{t_f} T(t)\sigma(r(t))c(r(t), d)dt$ where near and far bounds are t_n, t_f , and $T(t) = \exp\left(-\int_{t_n}^t \sigma(r(s))ds\right)$ and the camera ray is $r(t)$. $T(t)$ is the “accumulated transmittance along the ray from t_n to t , i.e., the probability that the ray travels from t_n to t without hitting any other particle” [14]. The color c and volume density σ are found by passing through the MLP at each point along the ray. To approximate the continuous integral, NeRF uses a “stratified sampling approach” [14], partitioning the interval $[t_n, t_f]$ into N bins, and drawing uniformly from each bin: $t_i \sim U\left[t_n + \frac{i-1}{N}(t_f - t_n), t_n + \frac{i}{N}(t_f - t_n)\right]$. This is how the MLP “[is] evaluated at continuous positions over the course of optimization” [14]. The authors use these “samples to estimate $C(r)$ with the quadrature rule” [14] by $\hat{C}(r) = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i(1 - \exp(-\sigma_i\delta_i))c_i$ Where $\delta_i = t_{i+1} - t_i$ is the “distance between adjacent samples” [14].

The point here is to make both the sampled colors (c_i) and densities (σ_i) “trivially differentiable” [14] thus NeRF can easily optimize through gradient descent, as it minimizes

the error between rendered images and source images.

NeRF uses a hierarchical sampling procedure: it optimizes both a coarse and a fine network to sample “free space and occluded regions” [14] efficiently. First the coarse network accepts a set of stratified samples N_c to evaluate, the output colors c_i and densities σ_i are used to compute weights: “ $w_i = T_i(1 - \exp(-\sigma_i\delta_i))v$ ” [14]. These weights are normalized to create a probability density function, and a second set of locations is sampled from this PDF, N_f , and “evaluate our ‘fine’ network at the union of the first and second set of samples, and compute the final rendered color of the ray $\hat{C}_f(r)$ using $N_c + N_f$ ” [14]. The loss calculated for each network is the “total squared error between the rendered and true pixel colors” [14]: $L = \sum_{r \in R} \left[\left| \hat{C}_c(r) - C(r) \right|_2^2 + \left| \hat{C}_f(r) - C(r) \right|_2^2 \right]$. R is the set of rays per batch, $C(r), \hat{C}_c(r), \hat{C}_f(r)$ “are the ground truth, coarse volume predicted, and fine volume predicted” [14].

The MLP encounters the same problems as the plenoptic function: “the scene representation [must be] consistent across different viewpoints while still capturing view-dependent effects (like reflections)” [14]. However the MLP has the appropriate tools to deal with it due to being probabilistic in nature: the authors restrict “the network to predict the volume density σ as a function of only the location x , while allowing the RGB color c to be predicted as a function of both location and viewing direction” [14].

The MLP first starts with “the input 3D coordinate x with 8 fully-connected layers (using ReLU activations and 256 channels per layer)” [14], then it outputs the volume density “ σ and a 256-dimensional feature vector” [14]. Then this feature vector and the camera ray’s viewing direction are concatenated. This combined input is “passed to one additional fully-connected layer (using a ReLU activation and 128 channels) that output the view-dependent RGB color” [14]. The final layer “(with a sigmoid activation [function]) outputs the emitted RGB radiance” [14]. They use adam with a learning rate “that begins at $5 * 10^{-4}$ and decays exponentially to $5 * 10^{-5}$ ” [14]. A single scene takes “around 100-300k iterations to converge on a single NVIDIA V100 GPU” [14].

NeRF maps “inputs to a higher dimensional space using high frequency functions” [14] then passes them to the network to fit data that is of higher frequency variation better, as the MLP is inclined to “learn[...] lower frequency functions” [14]. Removing the positional encoding that allows this “drastically decreases the model’s ability to represent high frequency geometry and texture, resulting in an oversmoothed appearance” [14].

COLMAP structure from motion is used to estimate “camera poses, intrinsics [(transformation, rotation)], and bounds for [...] real data” [14] which is supplemented with real ground truth “camera poses, intrinsics and bounds for synthetic data” [14]. The last state-of-the-art paved the way for the success of the neural network.

NeRF was a significant “improvement over baseline methods when rendering smooth paths of novel views.” [14]. The upcoming technique, although impressive in terms of accuracy and resolution compared to NeRF, the main change is that it goes from “(about 1-2 days)” [14] to “first real-time rendering with high quality for novel-view synthesis” [14].

3.2 3D Gaussian Splatting for Real-Time Radiance Field Rendering

As the current state-of-the-art, it is the first technique that enabled web apps that allow free 2D to 3D reconstruction over the internet that happen in seconds (for smaller gaussian splatting models), even text-to-2D-to-3D (Meshy.ai).

The base model, “trained for 30000 iterations” takes only “41m33s” [8], the method allows record speed inference and training times, with less than 1 GB of ram usage. Gaussian splatting also achieves “134 FPS [...] 160FPS” rendering speed, which means yes, that it produces full 3D environments that can be navigated due to the speed of inference that is possible with it. This was achieved before gaussian splatting with Mip-NeRF 360 [2], which was a specialised variant designed for unbounded 360 scenes that still fails to accomplish the same finer detail and speed gaussian splatting achieves.

The primary objective of the model is to “optimize a scene representation that allows high-quality novel view synthesis, starting from a sparse set of structure from motion points without normals”. COLMAP structure from motion created the sparse set similar to NeRF, however in this instance gaussian splatting essentially takes the role of multi-view stereo in fleshing out a 3D mesh, albeit using a vastly different technique.

3D gaussians “are differentiable and can be easily projected to 2D splats allowing fast α blending for rendering” [8]. The authors defined gaussians as: $G(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{2}(x)^T \Sigma^{-1}(x)}$ The gaussians start from 3D, and they are projected for rendering to 2D. given transform of a view W the covariance matrix is : $\Sigma' = JW\Sigma W^T J^T$ [8].

One can directly optimize for the gaussians, but they have “physical meaning only when they are positive semi-definite” [8], and a direct gradient descent would not be “constrained to produce such valid matrices” [8] nor update steps to remedy this “can very easily create invalid covariance matrices” [8].

The covariance matrix Σ can be defined as a “configuration of an ellipsoid” [8]. $\Sigma = RSS^T R^T$ where S is a scaling matrix and R is the rotation matrix. The one of the aims is to find the optimal ellipsoid configuration; to optimise for both variables. This, “anisotropic covariance” [8], allows “3D Gaussians to adapt to the geometry of different shapes in captured scenes” [8].

The core of the model establishes a “dense set of 3D gaussians accurately representing the scene for free-view synthesis” [8]. It optimizes for the “positions p , α , and Σ [...] and color c of each gaussian” [8]. The technique is “based on successive iterations of rendering and comparing” [8], in case in an iteration a gaussian gets placed incorrectly, the optimization has the ability “destroy or move geometry” [8].

The authors employ “Stochastic Gradient Descent” [8] with their custom “fast rasterization” [8] algorithm, which will be referenced later, which allowed them to train in minutes and perform real-time inference. The model starts with a sigmoid activation function for α “to obtain smooth gradients” [8], continues with an exponential activation function for Σ . Then the initial covariance matrix is estimated with an “exponential decay scheduling technique” [8]:

$\mathcal{L} = (1 - \lambda)\mathcal{L}_1 + \lambda\mathcal{L}_{D-SSIM}$ $\lambda = 0.2$ in all tests. According to the loss function, the authors start representing the scene with a sparse set of gaussians, and then they “densify every 100 iterations and remove any gaussians that are transparent [$\alpha < \epsilon_\alpha$]” [8]. The densifying process happens most in “empty areas” [8] and also where “gaussians cover large areas in the scene” [8], this is checked for with a “average magnitude view-space

position gradients above a threshold $\tau_{pos} = 0.0002$. As one can observe from Figure 3.1: For empty areas, one “clone[s] the [existing] gaussians [and...] mov[e] it in the direction of the positional gradient” [8]. For scenes with large gaussians, one “split [large gaussians] into smaller gaussians” by changing the old large gaussian with two smaller ones (“by a factor of $\phi = 1.6$ ” [8]). Empty regions are called “under-reconstruction” [8] and areas with large yet few gaussians are called “over-reconstruction” [8].

Figure 3.1: Their adaptive Gaussian densification scheme. *Top row (under-reconstruction)*: When small-scale geometry (black outline) is insufficiently covered, they clone the respective Gaussian. *Bottom row (over-reconstruction)*: If small-scale geometry is represented by one large splat, they split it in two.

The custom rasterizer the authors implemented allowed for “fast overall rendering and fast sorting to allow approximate α -blending” [8]. The rasterizer “pre-sort[s] primitives for an entire image at a time, [achieving cheaper sorting than per-pixel methods]” [8]. The rasterizer “split[s] the screen into 16x16 tiles, and then proceeds to cull 3D gaussians against the view frustum and each tile [only gaussians with 99 percent confidence interval in intersecting the view frustum are kept]” [8]. Then each gaussian is instantiated by “the number of tiles they overlap” [8] and they are assigned a key that “combines view space depth and tile ID” [8]. Then, to start α -blending, an initial sorting, “a single fast GPU radix sort” [8] based on the keys is performed. The blending is an approximation, however as it is not per-pixel, it “greatly enhances training and rendering performance without visible artifacts” [8]. Then for each tile a list of gaussians is determined based on “first and last depth-sorted entry that splats” [8]. These gaussian splat lists are traversed “front-to-back” [8] to gain the color and α values of the tile. When “target saturation $\alpha = 1$ is reached, the corresponding thread stops.” [8]. This is the “only stopping criterion” [8]. This enables the technique to “handle scenes with an arbitrary varying depth complexity” [8]. When performing backward pass the authors “recover the full sequence of blended points per-pixel in the forward pass.” [8] which they achieve by traversing the “per-tile lists again” [8]. The gradient computation for gaussians starts from the deepest splats, and for each pixel an overlap of splats will be checked only if the latest splat covering the pixel has depth higher than or equal to the current splat. The gradients require the “accumulated opacity values” [8] which is the sum of the α values of initially-blended gaussians. This is the forward pass. In the backward pass, one can recover the intermediate opacity values from each gaussian by dividing the stored final accumulated opacity by each points’ individual opacity, which is a coefficient required for the gradient computation [8].

This was the implementation of the initial gaussian splatting, which has branched into hundreds of different versions suitable and better-performing at each task. It might be more accurate to call it the state-of-the-art paradigm for 3D reconstruction for now.

The final section will show a side-by-side comparison of all explained methods up until now, in terms of compute time, the results they were capable of and evolution, it will include also a summary from the author.

Chapter 4

Results and Comparison

Table 4.1: Techniques and representative output examples. Replace figure paths with actual images.

Technique	Output (Results)		
<p>The Lumigraph [6]</p>	<p>(a) 256 line samples</p>		
	<p>(b) reconstruction from (a)</p>		
	<p>(c) 100 line samples</p>		
	<p>(d) reconstruction from (c) Figure 18</p>		

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Technique	Output (Results)
<p>Light Field Rendering [9]</p>	<p>Figure 14: Example images from four light fields, extracted during a typical interactive viewing session.</p> <p>Figure 15: Images extracted from compressed light fields</p> <p>(a) Buddha. <i>Vector dimension:</i> 12 <i>Compression:</i> 45:1</p> <p>(b) Lion. <i>Vector dimension:</i> 48 <i>Compression:</i> 118:1</p>
<p>View-Dependent Texture Mapping [5]</p>	<p>Figure 16: Novel views of the scene generated from four original photographs. These are frames from an animated movie in which the facade rotates continuously. The depth is computed from model-based stereo and the frames are made by compositing image-based renderings with view-dependent texture-mapping.</p>
<p>Unstructured Lumigraph Rendering [3]</p>	<p>Figure 10: Operation of our scheme for handling resolution issues: (a) shows the hallway scene with no consideration of resolution and (b) shows the same viewpoint rendered with consideration of resolution. Below each image is the corresponding camera blending field.</p>
<p>Structure from Motion (SfM)</p>	<p>N/A</p>

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Technique	Output (Results)
Photo Tourism [19]	<p data-bbox="552 517 1390 555">Figure 5: Screenshots from the explorer interface. Left: a view looking down on the Prague dataset, rendered in a non-photorealistic style. Right: when the user visits a photo, that photo appears at full-resolution, and information about it appears in a pane on the left.</p>
COLMAP [18]	<p data-bbox="539 741 1386 770">Fig. 1. Reconstructions for Louvre, Todai-ji, Paris Opera, and Astronomical Clock.</p>
Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [14]	<p data-bbox="204 1171 464 1249">Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [14]</p> <p data-bbox="788 1601 1281 1621">Ground Truth NeRF (ours) LLFF [28] SRN [42] NV [24]</p>

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Technique	Output (Results)				
3D Gaussian Splatting [8]	Ground Truth	Ours	Mip-NeRF360	InstantNGP	Plenoxels

Technique	Year	Required Compute	Importance
The Lumigraph	1996	Strictly limited to the lab due to “high consumption of memory and storage”.	One of the first to render photorealistic novel views of real objects, virtually independent of geometry or illumination complexity.
Light Field Rendering	1996	workstation level hardware of the time was able to execute creation of 192x192 images in “30-230ms” given that the 4D light field was established (which required compute and storage similar to model weights of high parameter models today).	This was the first to generate novel views with massive image compression for rendering “(100:1)” and required less compute than the lumigraph
View-dependent Texture Mapping	1996	was very computationally intensive and “did not scale well with many input photos”.	With only a few photos, could produce superior renderings to many other methods of its time. These three methods proved that consumer use level novel view synthesis is possible.
Unstructured Lumigraph Rendering	2001	GPU-accelerated, the performance was similar to old lumigraph with similar data	Was a mixture of view-dependent texture mapping and the lumigraph. It proved to be better than both although it still suffered from most of their drawbacks
Structure from Motion (SfM)	1981	Was impressively cheap computationally even for its day: could run on a computer, the harder requirement was the data necessary to run the computation	The oldest algorithm in this table (certainly not the oldest of novel view synthesis) gave birth to the structure from motion paradigm which became the state of the art pre-deep-learning and still performs exceptionally. There are no results as this exact paper was more mathematical in nature.
Photo Tourism	2006	Required substantial processing on 2000s hardware. A run of 120 photos took “a few hours”. 2635 photos of Notre Dame visualization took about two weeks of processing.	Demonstrated SfM on bare, unstructured internet photos, even created an app for the consumer market it created for navigating a blend of collection of photos in 3D.
COLMAP	2016	Was publicly available and scaled to large datasets efficiently. First time a substantial SfM algorithm took only an order of minutes and hours in consumer hardware.	The state-of-the-art pre-deep learning, it still gets used today for reference datasets of deep-learning models achieving the same goal, and has impressive performance even compared to modern SOTA.
Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF)	2020	The initial NeRF was compute intensive, requiring many hours on nvidia gpus per scene “300k iterations”. Inference each frame for a 800x800 image required 30 seconds on an NVIDIA V100. The times are faster than older techniques, however with the requirement of orders of magnitudes more compute	Was one of the smallest neural networks at the time with a simple logic, yet it showed that a continuous volumetric photorealistic scene representation that is independent of scene complexity is possible. It was a breakthrough in quality of photorealism possible in 3D scenes and novel views.
3D Gaussian Splatting	2023	Fastest algorithm on this table, achieving training in minutes and able to perform real time rendering. It achieves convergence on a scene in 30-45 minutes versus 48 hours on a comparable NeRF scene training. It, on top of this, still improved upon the photorealism of scenes and was able to render up to 160 FPS.	As the current state-of-the-art, it can both run on consumer hardware for inference, can be trained with economical levels of compute and time, and still enabled photorealism and real time splatted VR worlds. It almost has achieved the goal of democratizing creating 3D digital art to the people at a very reasonable price. There are many variants of it that perform even faster and even better for a subset of tasks.

Table 4.2: Timeline of 2D-to-3D reconstruction and novel-view synthesis techniques.

Conclusion

Limitations and Open Challenges

Plenoptic (Light-based) methods require heavy compute for capture and storage; along with assuming static scenes and static lighting. Without enough scenes one observes aliasing artifacts and ultimately at the time only workstations were able to run it. View-dependent texture mapping depended on a coarse proxy and view weighting, which meant with fine details in a scene and geometry, disocclusions and movement would generate artifacts. Structure from motion and Multi-view stereo is heavily affected by small movement, blur artifacts and repetitive surfaces when achieving the optimal geometry. NeRF relies heavily on accurate poses, can overfit to training data and increasing resolution increases required compute exponentially. 3D Gaussian splatting has proven itself to be the most flexible and the best performing paradigm (it is state-of-the-art without losing in any area to its' predecessors). Even more recent examples (in this instance for 2D) can train faster than the eye can observe [23]. Though as scenes grow the required memory to complete inference increases, and still the existing benchmarks are quite immature. A live implementation within this thesis wasn't permitted since more modern (mainly deep learning) techniques here are very memory and compute intensive.

A Tale of Two Paradigms

Over the years this niche field has seen more and more attention, with subsequently higher compute and building up on the existing methods, up until COLMAP, which is a hand-crafted method of peak craftsmanship. The novel-view synthesis world before machine learning was a sharp, semi-niche tool that was being newly acknowledged for its vast possible consumer applications. The techniques built on top of each other directly and tried to solve the faults of the best that came before it.

The deep learning models that have succeeded in giving a meaningful level of performance compared to COLMAP with a much more expandable and scalable system (COLMAP is a severely optimized machine unlike these new approaches that still have time to mature). Have shifted the paradigm to solve every problem all at once (very similarly to current day frontier large language models), and to use adapted versions of the same networks to solve one's use case of the model better: in change giving the power to the one who wielded the model. NeRF and 3D Gaussian splatting are both generalist models with many variants that are more powerful than them at a subset of tasks. With these, novel view synthesis has become a widely available tool that still has yet to see peak commercial use, however, is being understood more. Unlike many things that have on paper have improved yet have become more fragile and costly (software, hardware, clothes, cars, houses, physical infrastructure, common goods and services, the list goes

on), novel-view synthesis has improved in photorealism (the main goal), robustness and have become cheaper and widely accessible to implement. It has never been so easy to create full meshes out of a few images (even one shot or using diffusion-generated images).

My Note

I've always wanted to enter the field of 3D graphics, as a result of my current craft (machine learning) having a very strong influence in the field it was only appropriate that I embarked on this journey. Far and few things I've had influence on in my life. I was afraid that these fields (3D graphics, design and game development) are hyper-competitive and I wasn't enough to perform. That was a disservice to myself, which I'm regaining step by step, this thesis is one of my steps.

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